

1 **BIOLOGICAL INVASIONS**

2 **ORIGINAL PAPER**

3 **Invariant and vulnerable food web components after bullfrog invasion**

4
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1 **Abstract**

2 Alien species introductions produce strong impacts on invaded communities, altering their structure, diversity and
3 functioning. These impacts are interrelated with changes in food web architecture. However, the reorganization or
4 robustness of food webs in the face of invasion is a phenomenon poorly considered in ecology and conservation practices.
5 In this article, we analyze the effects of the invasion of the American bullfrog, *Lithobates catesbeianus*, on the structure
6 and function of invaded food webs. Specifically, we analyzed the integration of energetic channels by top predators, the
7 relative use of alternative energetic paths by different functional groups and its dependence on body size among invaded
8 and uninvaded communities in Uruguay, South America. The integration of energetic paths at high trophic positions by
9 large body sized consumers was a pervasive feature of food webs among all studied ponds, in spite of turnover in top
10 predator identity and large changes in community composition. Bullfrog post-metamorphs presented high trophic positions,
11 integrating the primary producers and detritus paths, acting as apex predators in invaded food webs. The bullfrog tadpoles
12 presented intermediate positions and were associated with the detritivorous pathway. On the other hand, the relative
13 importance of the primary producers and detritus as carbon sources assimilated into the biomass of fish and invertebrates
14 was altered in invaded systems. The robustness in the integration pattern of energy channels is congruent with its proposed
15 central role in the stability of food webs. These results advance the understanding of the effect of invasions on key structural
16 features of food webs, notably underrepresented in the invasion literature.

17 **Keywords:** Aquatic community, Trophic path, Top predator, Food web stability, Stable isotope analysis, Paths coupling

18

19 **Introduction**

20 Identifying the structures and processes that confer stability to communities is a historical and central aim of ecology
21 (Kondoh 2003; May 2006; Garay-Narváez et al. 2013). The central role that the structure of food webs plays in community
22 stability was identified early in ecological studies (Pimm 1984). An important structural component in food webs are the
23 dynamics and coupling of energy channels (McCann et al. 2005; Rooney et al. 2006, 2008; Arim et al. 2007, 2010; Rooney
24 and McCann 2012; Potapov et al. 2019; Keppeler et al. 2021). Many of the food webs described, from aquatic and soils
25 ecosystems, present two major energy flow pathways with contrasting properties, the primary producer (also called “green
26 channel”) and the detrital energy channel (also called “brown channel”) (Rooney et al. 2006, 2008; Rooney and McCann
27 2012; Zhao et al. 2018). The producer path tends to have relatively low species diversity, low number of interactions, high
28 cycling speed, and strong interactions, compared with the detritus path (Rooney and McCann 2012). These pathways are
29 asymmetric in their rates of energy flow, total productivity and exchange rates (production:biomass ratios) (Rooney et al.
30 2006; Cordone et al. 2020). It has been proposed that the existence of these “fast-green” and “slow-brown” pathways
31 generate asynchronous energy flows in the food web, with the consequent stabilization of the biomass dynamic in the
32 whole community (Rooney et al. 2006; Wang et al. 2019; Tilman et al. 1998). Likewise, theoretical and empirical
33 approaches identify the coupling of different energy pathways by large predators at high trophic positions, as a pattern that
34 stabilizes populations and the entire community (Rooney et al. 2006; Romanuk et al. 2006; Arim et al. 2010; Rooney and
35 McCann 2012; Keppeler et al. 2021). Each one of the energy channels varies temporarily in biomass and richness
36 determining differences in resource availability (Ying et al. 2020). Consequently, when the green and brown energy paths
37 are decoupled, they are prone to present oscillations (Rooney et al. 2006, 2008). Large body size predators, at high trophic
38 positions, are able to feed in a large range of prey, directing their consumption to more abundant resources and rapidly

1 shifting in prey type (Beckerman et al. 2010; Valdovinos et al. 2010; Jackson et al. 2011; Heckmann et al. 2012; Rooney
2 and McCann 2012; Potapov et al. 2019). This plasticity causes predation pressure on the magnified path to increase, which
3 also reduces predation pressure on alternative energy paths. This capacity for sequential top-down pressure change would
4 stabilize and maintain the trophic web diversity (Rooney et al. 2006; Rooney and McCann 2012). Summarizing, the
5 coupling of energy channels may enhance the two components of community stability, species persistence and fluctuations
6 in biomass (May 1974; Dunne et al. 2005). First, species persistence is enhanced when large predators are able to satisfy
7 their large energetic demands by the use of different energy sources. Secondly, variation in biomass dynamics is attenuated
8 when predators switch between energy channels on the base of their relative biomasses, restricting the increase in some
9 functional groups when they become dominant but fostering their growth when rare.

10 One of the major global change drivers is the invasion of alien species, which generate new interactions in native
11 communities, affecting their trophic webs by various mechanisms (Bruno et al. 2005; Rodriguez 2006; Strong and Leroux
12 2014; Gallardo et al. 2016; David et al. 2017). The effect of novel exotic species on food webs does not necessarily imply
13 the extinction of native species. Several studies report changes in the configuration and function of food webs, such as
14 changes in chain length, connectance, complexity and abundances at certain trophic levels (e.g. Woodward and Hildrew
15 2002; Salvaterra et al. 2013; Ives et al. 2019). Changes in the interaction between native species after introduction of exotic
16 ones to the food web have been reported (Vander Zanden et al. 1999; Holgerson et al. 2022). These changes in trophic
17 habits have been related to alterations in the availability and/or flow of nutrients (Strayer et al. 1999; Byrnes et al. 2007;
18 Miehls et al. 2009; Pereira-Garbero et al. 2013; Strong and Leroux 2014; Ives et al. 2019). Although, there are stabilizing
19 properties of ecosystems that buffer the effects of invasions, those invasions (especially when the invader belongs to a new
20 functional group, as novel top predators) can influence food web structure and thus ecosystem function (Woodward and
21 Hildrew 2002; Kimbro et al. 2009; Carey and Wahl 2010; Nuñez et al. 2010; Garay-Narváez et al. 2013; Thomsen et al.
22 2014; Rettig and Smith 2021). Consequently, invasions are probably impacting the coupling structure of energy channels
23 by top predators, altering food web and ecosystem stability (Ives et al. 2019). Notably, while the coupling of energy
24 channels is a main topic of attention in food web theory, it has been rarely considered in invasion ecology.

25 The American bullfrog, *Lithobates catesbeianus* (Shaw 1802), is an aquatic amphibian categorized as one of the most
26 dangerous invasive species worldwide (Kumschick et al. 2017; Jorgewich-Cohen et al. 2020). It is a species with a complex
27 life cycle, so its invasion implies the addition of at least two trophospecies to native communities: post-metamorphs and
28 larvae (which typically overwinter in permanent ponds). Both phases present exceptionally large body sizes and commonly
29 reach high population densities (Govindarajulu et al. 2006). While post-metamorphs are important top predators, tadpoles
30 feed on inferior and basal resources (Ruibal and Laufer 2012; Jancowski and Orchard 2013). Regarding impacts at the
31 community level, a decrease in abundance and richness of native amphibians has been reported (Hecnar and M'Closkey
32 1997a; Li et al. 2011; Gobel et al. 2019a). Contrary to what happens with most amphibian species, the bullfrog has the
33 ability to coexist with fish. Fish strongly determine pond community structure, limiting the richness of invertebrates and
34 amphibians (Scheffer et al. 2006; Semlitsch et al. 2015). The evidence indicates that the bullfrog eludes this pattern (Hecnar
35 and M'Closkey 1997b; Babbitt et al. 2003). Moreover, several works show positive relationships with fishes—both native
36 and exotic—(Maezono and Miyashita 2003; Adams et al. 2003; Laufer et al. 2008; Gobel et al. 2019a). Invaded
37 communities show higher fish densities and lower native tadpole densities, as well as an increase in the sizes of tadpoles
38 and fish. These changes in the community structure patterns, with alterations in the biomass of some components, suggest
39 an effect on the relative structure of the energy paths (Maezono and Miyashita 2003; Laufer et al. 2008; Gobel et al. 2019a).

1 Stable isotope analysis constitutes a compelling approach for the study of food web structure in general and the coupling
2 of energy channels in particular (Vander Zanden et al. 1999; Fry 2006). The range of carbon isotope values ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) observed
3 among species typically reflects the spectrum of energy sources used by each species and the relative amount of energy
4 obtained from each of the energy sources (e.g. Fry 2013). Consumers specializing in one kind of resource (detritus or
5 primary productivity) are observed at extreme ends of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, while species that balance the use of different energy
6 sources are observed at intermediate locations (Fry 2006; Rooney et al. 2006). On the other hand, nitrogen isotopes ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$)
7 are magnified in trophic interactions, representing the relative trophic position of species, the larger $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ the higher the
8 trophic position (Post 2002). Consequently, if top and large predators are coupling energy paths the use of the isotopic
9 space by species will be constrained, expecting that larger $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ are associated with intermediate locations in the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$
10 spectrum (Rooney et al. 2006; Arim et al. 2010). Thus, the effect of bullfrog invasion on the food web structure can be
11 evidenced by comparing the isotopic spaces of invaded and uninvaded communities. The role of persistent and abundant
12 bullfrog larvae is unclear. These larvae, that remove other amphibian larvae and are rarely consumed because of their large
13 body sizes, could be sequestering detritus resources. However, the reduction in detritivorous diversity and the large
14 bioturbation associated with the density and activity of bullfrog larvae can increase the availability of detritus resources
15 (Smith 1999; Ranvestel et al. 2004; Govindarajulu et al. 2006). In the first case the food web will increase its use of energy
16 from the green path while in the second it will increase the use of the brown path—detected by the displacement of species
17 location in the carbon isotopic space. The invasion of adult bullfrog typically involves a large change in the assembly of
18 top predator species of aquatic food webs—e.g. native amphibians, fishes and turtles. Uninvaded communities are expected
19 to show the coupling of energy paths by native top predators. Invaded communities can either present an asymmetric use
20 of energy channels by top large predators—concentrated at the end of the carbon isotopic space—or comply with the expected
21 balance of energy paths in spite of variations in community composition. Only with a detailed empirical exploration of
22 food web structure along invaded and uninvaded communities will it be possible to evidence the relative support associated
23 with the predictions of these plausible but opposite hypotheses.

24 Congruently, in this article we analyze the C and N stable isotopes values in invaded and uninvaded ponds with contrasting
25 community assemblies. Specifically, we analyzed i) the integration of energetic paths, ii) the relative use of energy paths
26 by different functional groups, iii) the trophic position-body size association and iv) the relative use of energy paths by
27 organisms of different body sizes. These patterns might evidence the effect of species invasions in those key elements of
28 food web architecture related with the coupling of energy paths, and consequently, with ecosystem stability.

29

30 **Materials and methods**

31 *Study site*

32 Aceguá (Cerro Largo Department) is a hilly area (approx. 220 m a.s.l.), at the northeastern Uruguayan border with Brazil
33 ($31^{\circ}53'36''\text{S}$, $54^{\circ}09'26''\text{W}$). Local land use is mostly extensive cattle and agriculture. This region hosts relatively high
34 biodiversity of fauna and flora (Grattarola et al. 2020). At this locality, a feral bullfrog population at the establishment
35 phase was registered in 2007. Later, in 2012, this population began the expansion, now invading 31 permanent artificial
36 ponds, built for agricultural purposes (Laufer et al. 2018). Local ponds house relatively well-known biological
37 communities, being fish and amphibians the most frequent vertebrates, and the bullfrog is the only exotic species reported.
38 Fish assemblage is dominated by the Characidae family (e.g. *Astyanax laiceps*, *Psalilodon eigenmanniorum*, *P. anisitsi*

1 and *Cheirodon interruptus*), omnivorous species which consume detritus, algae and small crustacean and insect larvae.
2 Less frequently, Siluriformes (e.g. *Callichthys callichthys*) are also part of the assembly (Gobel et al. 2019b). The
3 amphibian assembly consists of species with a wide distribution (e.g. *Boana pulchella*, *Pseudis minuta*), but also species
4 with restricted distribution to this ecoregion (e.g. *Scinax uruguayus*, *S. aromothyella*) (Laufer and Gobel 2017). In the
5 studied ponds, the most frequent tadpoles are *B. pulchella*, *Odontophrynus americanus*, *Pseudis minuta* and *Scinax* sp.
6 (comprising *S. granulatus* and *S. squalirostris*, undeterminable based on their descriptions). These tadpoles feed mainly
7 on primary producers and detritus, although they also consume low amounts of crustaceans and small insect larvae
8 (Echeverría et al. 2007). Other frequent vertebrates are the aquatic turtles *Trachemys dorbigni* and *Hydromedusa tectifera*,
9 both with a generalist diet (Grattarola et al. 2020).

10

11 *Field sampling and laboratory analysis*

12 We sampled two invaded and two uninvaded aquatic pond communities at this locality in April 2016. We selected these
13 ponds based on the known local American bullfrog distribution. The control (uninvaded) ponds were located near the
14 invasion front, and *L. catesbeianus* presence has not been recorded to date (Laufer et al. 2018; NG & GL personal
15 observation at 2020). Sampled ponds were selected according to omnivorous Characidae fish presence (one with and other
16 without fish, for the invaded and uninvaded category). These four systems that we use as a model, were carefully selected
17 based on prior knowledge about the physical, morphological, and community characteristics of the Aceguá ponds (i.e.
18 Laufer et al. 2018; Gobel et al. 2019a,b; Laufer et al. 2021). The analyzed ponds had similar characteristics, they were
19 permanent, with a range between 850 and 1780 m² areas. The pH of the sampled ponds ranged from 4.4 to 5.7 and the
20 conductivity from 46 to 122 µS/cm. These systems are inserted in the same land cover and land use (natural grasslands
21 with extensive cattle), so we expect that the path of the terrestrial detritus will be homogeneous between ponds. As the
22 considered systems have similar energy sources, we do not expect a variation in the differential $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ signal between the
23 ponds, which could alter our results. Likewise, the trophic position was in all cases corrected by the signal from the
24 producers of each pond. Because of limitations in the range of ponds with similar conditions but differing in the presence-
25 absence of bullfrogs, and because our attention towards food web architecture is extremely demanding in terms of local
26 community information (see below), the consideration of several replicates for each condition was hampered. However,
27 having monitored community structure in the area in previous research (Gobel et al. 2019a) we argue that these ponds are
28 well representative of each type of pond in regard to its community structure (i.e. ponds with fish and bullfrog, ponds
29 without fish and bullfrogs, ponds with fish and no bullfrog and ponds with no fish and bullfrog) and thus can be used as a
30 model to test for changes in food web architecture.

31 For stable isotope analysis, samples were taken from different basal sources, both autochthonous and allochthonous, and
32 from various consumers. In each system, grass of aquatic and terrestrial origin, filamentous algae, decomposing plant
33 matter, and cow feces were collected as the main basal resources. In addition, using a 20 mm diameter PVC cylinder, a 1
34 cm deep sediment sample was taken. Epiphyton was extracted by rinsing macrophytes with clean water and periphyton
35 through stone scraping. In each pond, at least three replicates of each type of sample were taken and were immediately
36 frozen at -20°C until later preparation for isotopic analysis.

37 Macroinvertebrates, amphibian larvae, Characidae fish, and turtles were collected using a seine fishing net (5 x 1 m area
38 and 0.5 cm mesh). Two standardized tows were made in each pond, one in the direction of the largest diameter and the

1 other of the smallest. From each collected taxon (species in vertebrate and family in invertebrates), between 5 and 20
2 specimens were taken for stable isotope analysis, covering the entire range of observed body sizes. For those cases where
3 the number of specimens collected was less than 5 individuals per species, more tows and/or handnets passes were carried
4 out, in plant areas and on the sediment, in order to obtain the adequate number of specimens for the analyses (Jackson et
5 al. 2011).

6 A slow paced nocturnal trail was performed by two expert researchers around the whole pond perimeter (Dodd 2010),
7 where adult specimens of *L. catesbeianus* and the native aquatic frog *Pseudis minuta* were collected. This native species
8 was especially considered since it shares habits with the bullfrog. It is an amphibian with a completely aquatic life cycle,
9 relatively persistent larvae and an adult predator (Huckembeck et al. 2012). Amphibians and fish were euthanized with an
10 overdose of eugenol (Underwood and Anthony 2013), following the protocol approved by the committee for ethics in
11 animal research (CEUA-MNHN). Then, the specimens were determined at species level using a taxonomic key (e.g.
12 Ziegler and Maneyro 2008; Serra et al. 2014) and measured. Snout to tail peduncle length was measured in fish (Standard
13 length STL), snout to tip length in tadpoles (TL) and snout-vent length in post-metamorphic amphibians (SVL).
14 Immediately, these specimens were dissected to extract a portion of muscle, dorsal in the case of fish, of the tail in tadpoles,
15 and of the hind legs in post-metamorphic amphibians. The turtles were measured in the field, where a skin sample was
16 taken from their tails and then they were returned to the pond. All samples were immediately frozen at -20°C and
17 transferred to the laboratory for conditioning.

18 In the laboratory, the samples were conditioned for the analysis following standardized procedures (e.g. Levin and Currin
19 2012). Grass, cow feces, filamentous algae, decomposing plant material, and sediment were washed with distilled water
20 and analyzed under a stereomicroscope to extract animal remains. The periphyton and epiphyton samples were filtered
21 with GF/C filters to remove the water. The invertebrates were determined at family level and measured (total body length,
22 except for Coenagrionidae and Ephemeroptera which excluded the abdomen in the measurement), washed and the hard
23 parts (e.g. elytra) were extracted and, in the case of the larger invertebrates (e.g. Belostomatidae), the digestive system.
24 Muscle and skin samples of the vertebrates were washed and conditioned. The complete list of consumers analyzed can be
25 found in Online Resource 1. Finally, all samples were dried for 48 hours at 60°C and encapsulated in tin capsules (Levin
26 and Currin 2012). Once conditioned, the samples were sent to the Center for Stable Isotopes of the University of New
27 Mexico, where the analysis of stable isotopes was performed using a continuous-flow isotope ratio mass spectrometer.
28 Finally, the correction proposed by Post et al. (2007, equation 3) was carried out for all animal tissue samples, to reduce
29 noise signals in the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values due to differences in the lipid composition of their tissues.

30

31 *Estimation of biomass contribution and trophic position*

32 Bayesian mixing models were used to evaluate the energy pathways contributions to different consumers (Parnell et al.
33 2013). These analyses allow evaluating the coupling of energy pathways in the top consumers (e.g. in case that the two
34 analyzed pathways contribute to the biomass of consumers). In these models, the sources of primary producers and those
35 of allochthonous were grouped for each pond (Fry 2013). The signal of epiphyton, periphyton and filamentous algae was
36 considered as primary producers path, and cow feces, terrestrial vegetation, detritus of plant origin and sediment as detritus
37 path (of allochthonous origin). Trophic Enrichment Factor (TEF) values taken from the literature were used for the different
38 taxonomic groups. For macroinvertebrates, a fractionation of 2.5 ± 0.16 (mean \pm SD) was considered for nitrogen, and

1 0.35 ± 0.25 for carbon, following the review by Caut et al. (2009). For anura larvae, a fractionation of 1.98 ± 0.17 and
2 1.69 ± 0.12 was used for nitrogen and carbon respectively (Schiesari et al. 2009). For fish, a nitrogen fractionation for
3 omnivorous fish of 3.4 ± 1.1 was considered according to the meta-analysis carried out by Bunn et al. (2013) and the
4 carbon fractionation value of 0.4 ± 1.3 proposed by Post (2002). Finally, for bullfrog post-metamorphs and turtles, a
5 nitrogen fractionation of 2.3 ± 0.18 and a carbon fractionation of 1.3 ± 0.3 was considered according to McCutchan et al.
6 (2003). We performed these analyses at the population level using the function “siarmcmcdirichletv4” and at the individual
7 level using “siarsolomcmcv4” using the SIAR package (Parnell et al. 2013). Each model was run with 500,000 iterations
8 and a burn-in of 50,000 times.

9 The trophic position of consumers was estimated, following the standard formula (Vander Zanden et al. 1997; Post 2002):

10
$$Trophic\ position = [(\delta^{15}N_{consumer} - \delta^{15}N_{base}) / TEF] + 1$$

11 where TEF is the nitrogen fractionation value and 1 represents the theoretical trophic level of the primary producers. The
12 mean between the autochthonous and allochthonous basal sources of each pond was used to estimate the trophic position.
13 Specific TEFs were used for each taxonomic group, corresponding to those used in the mixing models (see above).

14

15 *Statistical analysis*

16 The relationship between the maximum trophic position ($\sim\delta^{15}N$) and the coupling in energy sources ($\sim\delta^{13}C$) used by species
17 was analyzed by quantile regressions (Cade and Noon 2003). Since the base of the food web consists of resources with
18 contrasting $\delta^{13}C$, when assimilating both pathways, predators should be located at the top of the $\delta^{15}N$ signal and at the
19 center of the $\delta^{13}C$ (integrating both sources of resources). The variable $\delta^{13}C$ was centered to standardize variations in the
20 different communities analyzed. The effects of native fish and the invasive bullfrogs were analyzed, as well as the
21 interaction between these effects. Models were selected with the AIC criterion and the weight of evidence (Burnham and
22 Anderson 2002). A stepwise model selection was used to advance the identification of plausible models.

23 For each community, the relative importance of both energy paths in consumer biomass was evaluated. The change in
24 invertebrate and Characidae fish proportion of allochthonous biomass was compared among sites with and without
25 bullfrog, through an Analysis of Variance test. In order to consider the pond identity effect, this variable was included into
26 the model as a factor. For these analyses, we used each individual value of proportion of allochthonous biomass as a
27 replicate. Native tadpoles were excluded because of their low frequencies in the invaded ponds. Due to the great variation
28 in the different families of macroinvertebrate trophic habits, and in order to control possible biases in the comparisons, we
29 evaluated differences in the taxonomic composition between communities, using the Jaccard similarity test. Then, we
30 performed a linear model to explore the effect of individual body size on the proportion of allochthonous carbon assimilated
31 and trophic position. For each assembly (Characidae fish, native tadpoles and macroinvertebrates), we perform independent
32 models, using least squares regression. The individual proportions of allochthonous biomass and trophic position was
33 considered as the dependent variable; body size and bullfrog presence (and its interaction) were the independent variables.
34 Native tadpole body sizes were log transformed because of their nonlinear association with trophic position and energy
35 sources and to satisfy model assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity. Furthermore, the proportion of allochthonous
36 carbon assimilated and trophic position in relation to body size was evaluated for both post-metamorphs and larvae of *L.*
37 *catesbeianus* by linear models. Model selection was made by the Likelihood ratio test (LRT) (Zuur et al. 2007). In all

1 cases, we considered $\alpha = 0.05$ as statistically significant and the analyses were performed in the R software (R Core Team
2 2021).

3

4 **Results**

5 Integration of energetic paths by species at higher trophic positions was a preponderant pattern in all the analyzed pond
6 communities, independently of the presence of fishes or bullfrogs (Figure 1). The 99th percentile of individual $\delta^{15}\text{N}$
7 presented a cubic relationship with $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and a significant interaction with the presence of fish and bullfrog in the pond.
8 However, must be noted that the qualitative pattern was the same for all the analyzed communities, independent of the
9 predators taxonomic identity (fish, amphibians and/or turtles; native or exotic), following an inverse U-shaped trend in
10 which species at higher trophic positions have a balanced use of energy sources (Figure 1, Online Resource 2).

11 Macroinvertebrates and Characidae fish assemblies showed significant differences in the assimilation of allochthonous
12 carbon into their biomass in the invaded and uninvaded systems (Figure 2). While the macroinvertebrates showed a lower
13 proportion of allochthonous carbon assimilated into their biomass in the invaded systems ($F_{1,50} = 20.0$, $p < 0.001$), fish
14 exhibited a higher proportion ($F_{1,56} = 135.0$, $p < 0.001$). The pattern of fish assemblage increase in the proportion of
15 allochthonous supported biomass was also observed at species level (*A. laticeps*, *P. anisitsi* and *C. interruptus*), with the
16 Bayesian mixing models at the taxonomic group level. This analysis also showed low allochthonous supported biomass
17 for most of the invertebrate taxa in the invaded ponds (Figure 3).

18 Body size presented a significant association with the fraction of biomass assimilated from allochthonous sources along
19 all the taxa considered. Macroinvertebrates assimilation of allochthonous sources increased with body size in all systems
20 ($F_{1,49} = 9.27$; $P = 0.004$) but having a significantly higher proportion in uninvaded ponds ($F_{1,49} = 23.3$; $P < 0.001$). The
21 main difference observed between invaded and uninvaded ponds was a shift in the fraction of allochthonous biomass, and
22 not a change in taxonomic identity (Jaccard similarity between communities = 0.75; Online Resource 1). The
23 macroinvertebrates of the invaded ponds had a fraction of allochthonous consumption 15% lower than in the uninvaded
24 ones. Likewise, in all ponds, the larger individuals presented 15% more of their biomass being subsidized from the
25 allochthonous path than the smaller body sizes (Figure 4a). Native tadpoles also exhibited an increase in the fraction of
26 allochthonous biomass assimilated with the logarithm of body size, going from 50 to 60%, between small and large sizes
27 ($F_{1,10} = 19.2$; $P = 0.001$), without significant differences between invaded and uninvaded ponds ($F_{1,10} = 0.03$; $P = 0.9$;
28 Figure 4b).

29 Fish did not change the proportion of allochthonous assimilation in their biomass with body size in the uninvaded pond,
30 as happened in the invaded system. Conversely, fish at the invaded pond significantly increased their allochthonous
31 supported biomass along their body size range. Fish that coexisted with bullfrogs presented a proportion of 50%
32 allochthonous supported biomass in the smallest sizes and a proportion of 75% in the largest sizes, while fish in the control
33 site (uninvaded pond) presented a contribution from allochthonous source of approximately 30%, independently of
34 individual body size (Figure 4c). In the selected model, the interaction between body size and bullfrog presence was
35 statistically significant ($F_{1,54} = 38.7$, $P < 0.001$).

36 Macroinvertebrates, amphibians and fish trophic position exhibited a significant association with body size (Figure 4).
37 Macroinvertebrates decreased trophic position with body size ($F_{1,46} = 7.9$; $P = 0.007$), being on average 0.7 higher in

1 invaded ponds ($F_{1,46} = 12.5$; $P < 0.001$; Figure 4d). Native tadpoles also decreased trophic position with log of body size
2 ($F_{1,9} = 37.4$; $P < 0.001$; Figure 4e), unchanged between invaded and uninvaded systems ($F_{1,9} = 3.0$; $P = 0.1$). On the contrary,
3 fish evidenced an increase in the trophic position with body size ($F_{1,54} = 21.7$; $P < 0.001$), being significantly higher in the
4 uninvaded site, with an average difference of 0.3 ($F_{1,54} = 32.0$; $P < 0.001$; Figure 4f).

5 Post-metamorphic *L. catesbeianus* exhibited a significant association between the fraction of allochthonous supported
6 biomass and body size, but a relatively low explained variance ($F_{1,18} = 7.7$, $P = 0.01$; $r\text{-sqrt} = 0.26$; Figure 5a). Post-
7 metamorphic bullfrogs presented a proportion of 60% allochthonous supported biomass in the smallest sizes and a
8 proportion of 80% in the largest sizes. Bullfrog tadpoles showed a positive association between body size and the
9 proportion of allochthonous biomass ($F_{1,12} = 23.3$, $P < 0.001$; $r\text{-sqrt} = 0.63$). During this developmental stage, the fraction
10 of biomass from allochthonous sources ranged from 40 to 70%, increasing along the observed body size gradient (Figure
11 5b). Bullfrog individual trophic position did not show a relationship with body size, neither for the post-metamorphs ($F_{1,18}$
12 $= 0.5$; $P = 0.5$), nor for their larvae ($F_{1,12} = 0.004$; $P = 0.9$). The post-metamorphs showed a trophic position that varied
13 between 2.5 and 4, while the larvae varied between 2.3 and 2.6 (Figure 5c, 5d).

14

15 **Discussion**

16 The consequences of biological invasions on biodiversity patterns and stability are mediated by changes in food web
17 architecture (McCann 2007). However, the study of these changes is underrepresented in the invasion literature (Simberloff
18 2004). In this research we analyzed the impact of invasions in key structural features of food webs. We observed both
19 invariant and altered components of food web organization putatively determined by bullfrog invasion. On one hand,
20 despite the invasion and strong changes in community organization, the integration of energetic paths by large predators
21 at upper trophic positions remains as a pervasive feature of food webs (Figure 1). On the other hand, the relative use of
22 energy paths by different functional groups, as well as its dependence on body size, was significantly impacted by bullfrog
23 invasion. From now on, we will first discuss our methodological approach, followed by the role of the bullfrog in food
24 webs, the alterations in the consumption of the native assemblages generated by its invasion, and finally we will discuss
25 the stability of the energy pathway coupling in the context of these structural changes.

26 This work involved a compromise between the trophic and taxonomic resolution of the communities and the number of
27 systems that we were able to analyze. Considering the aforementioned hypotheses, we opted for a fine description of food
28 web and community structure rather than having several ponds with imprecise information about the key structural features
29 under analysis. However, environmental variables such as pond area, pH, vegetation cover or cattle density could be
30 relevant determinants of the analyzed patterns (e.g. Schalk et al. 2017). Aware of the replication limitation, we devoted
31 our attention to the identification of ponds with similar environmental conditions, not expecting a hidden effect of these
32 variables masked in the patterns herein reported. However, the strength and nature of the results may differ between
33 systems, affecting the universe of possible inferences from our results. For example, in highly productive systems, where
34 the green path would be magnified, we would expect a shift in the observed pattern towards this path (i.e. higher
35 consumption of green path) or a dampening of the observed changes (i.e. all components maintain green path consumption
36 independent of body size and if the system is invaded or not). In spite of this, the path coupling is emerging as a general
37 pattern along aquatic and terrestrial food webs (Rooney and McCann 2012), and given the robustness it showed against
38 changes in predators, we expect it to remain in ponds with different environmental gradients. Although there is a lack of

1 variability within each type of pond analyzed due to the lack of replication, in some aspects such as the energetic pathways
2 present we assume that systems might behave similarly due to their general homogeneity in terms of available resources.
3 For example, all the ponds in the network analyzed in the region (Laufer et al. 2018; Gobel et al. 2019a) either have algae
4 as basal resources or terrestrial detritus from surrounding grasslands, which are expected to be isotopically similar. The
5 focus of this work on the structure and function of the trophic web aims to contribute to aspects of invasion theory where
6 there is scarce available knowledge. This decision has the cost of the limits of all natural experiments where the causal
7 direction can be opposite to the process considered (Shiple 2016). Recognizing these limitations, this contribution is one
8 of the first pieces of evidence about the effect of the bullfrog invasion on the structure and functioning of energy pathways
9 in native trophic networks

10 Our observations confirm bullfrog is a generalist predator with high plasticity and an exceptional capacity to exploit local
11 resources (e.g. Jancowski and Orchard 2013). Evidence from the study site and elsewhere show that bullfrog is able to feed
12 on practically any prey it can ingest, from small insects to vertebrates, or even conspecifics (Laufer et al. 2021). Surely, its
13 ability to integrate different trophic pathways sustain these large body sized predator populations, with high-energy
14 requirements. In fact, in our studied systems the isotopic signal observations evidenced that adult bullfrog integrated
15 between 39 and 70% of carbon from the debris pathway. In spite of the several studies analyzing bullfrog diet, no attention
16 was previously devoted to these features. The insertion patterns of individuals in the food web exhibit a strong dependence
17 on body size, with variations in their consumption of different energy pathways (Woodward et al. 2005; Arim et al. 2010;
18 Jardine et al. 2017). On the other hand, in this study bullfrog tadpoles were identified as intermediate omnivores, in a
19 similar trophic position to predatory insects and only below top predators. Although bullfrog tadpoles have a generalized
20 anatomical oral disc configuration (Altig and Johnston 1989), their large body size might allow them to consume animal
21 prey. Congruently, previous studies indicate that these tadpoles may be preying on eggs and early stages of different species
22 (Schiesari et al. 2009; Ruibal and Laufer 2012). Furthermore, our results also support that the increase in energy demand
23 with body size is attended by an increase in the proportion of detritus, or detritivores, that are consumed. Almost 60% of
24 the biomass of the largest bullfrog larvae came from the detritus path, while this value does not reach 40% in the smallest
25 individuals. Large body sized individuals must include in their intake a significant fraction of the detritivorous path,
26 although it is of lower quality because of its high proportion of recalcitrant carbon (Thorp and DeLong 2002). These
27 abundant, low quality resources sustain their populations with important biomass and energy requirements (Arim et al.
28 2010; Jardine et al. 2017). Despite this significant change in resource origin, bullfrog larvae maintained the same trophic
29 position, regardless of their body size. This absence of changes can be explained by the absence of morphological predation
30 traits, which restrict its consumption of large prey at higher trophic positions. Our findings represent a significant advance
31 in the understanding of bullfrog ecology and the determinants of its successful invasions around the world, as well as on
32 the mechanisms behind its impact on invaded systems (see also Holgerson et al. 2022).

33 In these communities, bullfrog invasion produced a strong reduction in the abundances of native tadpoles (Gobel et al.
34 2019a). The almost disappearance of larvae of native anurans preclude any further analyses about the impact of the
35 invasions in this assembly (Figure 4). The contrasting pattern observed in fish and macroinvertebrate species among
36 invaded and uninvaded communities must also be highlighted. The energy sources supporting these functional groups were
37 significantly different along invaded communities. However, while fish species increased the proportion of resources
38 obtained from the detritus energy path the opposite was true for macroinvertebrates. In invaded ponds, macroinvertebrates
39 and fish presented a consumption of resources from the detritus path of approximately 40% and 60% respectively, while

1 in uninvaded ponds the proportions are reversed, being 60% for invertebrates and 40% for fish (Figure 2). This trend might
2 respond to a larger consumption of periphyton by macroinvertebrates and of detritivorous prey (or direct detritus) by fish
3 along invaded ponds, (Online Resource 2, Gobel et al. 2019b). Furthermore, these patterns are amplified with fish body
4 size, in which the use of the detritus path reaches a 70% in the largest individuals from invaded ponds (Figure 4). Turnover
5 in species composition may explain these trends but we did not observe changes in invertebrate species composition,
6 suggesting changes in species diet and their associated functional roles. This phenomenon of consumption shift in species
7 that co-occur with invasive bullfrogs has also been reported elsewhere (Holgerson et al. 2022). The variability and plasticity
8 in the consumption of different paths between individuals of the same species can result in an adaptive capacity, with
9 unknown effects on the stability of the trophic webs (Elliott Smith et al. 2021). Furthermore, macroinvertebrates have the
10 ability to alter their consumption based on the availability of resources (Entekin et al. 2020). Possibly, in invaded ponds
11 macroinvertebrates shift towards the green path due either to a lower use of this resource by vertebrates or a displacement
12 of invertebrates from the brown path by vertebrates because of competition, direct consumption, predation avoidance
13 behavior or direct interferences. Indeed, given that most algae on these systems grow attached to macrophytes, a
14 displacement of macroinvertebrates from the bottom to macrophyte patches—seeking refuge from predation or because
15 bioturbation- may promote a diet including more algal resources (Hansson et al. 2010).

16 The three most abundant fish species (*A. laticeps*, *P. anisitsi* and *C. interruptus*), had a high assimilation of detritus (Figure
17 3). Local diet studies report an omnivorous consumption for these three species (Gobel et al. 2019b), so we assume that
18 their decrease in trophic position probably was associated with a greater availability of basal resources in the brown path.
19 In fact, the pattern that we have identified for these fish in invaded water bodies was an increase in the abundance of larger
20 sizes (Laufer et al. 2008; Gobel et al. 2019a). Bullfrog presence in a pond could generate an availability of resources
21 associated with this path. This release of resources by invasive species is a frequent phenomenon, affecting environmental
22 conditions and ecosystem functioning (reviewed by Gallardo et al. 2016). This type of positive interaction between invasive
23 and native species has been scarcely explored, representing a priority for understanding the whole range of mechanisms
24 impacted by biological invasions (Gallien and Carboni 2017). The pattern reported herein supports the idea that the access
25 to more resources from the brown paths in larger fish sustains their increase in densities. Bullfrog larvae also increased the
26 assimilation of the detritus path with increasing body size (Figure 4 and 5). Both fish and bullfrog larvae had similar
27 biomass fraction from the detritus path. This suggests that the support of large bullfrog tadpoles and fish populations would
28 be related to a very similar trophic pathway. The high densities of bullfrog larvae and their high mobility generate pond
29 bioturbation (Ranvestel et al. 2004), which could amplify the detritus path by making detritus available to other community
30 components, reducing light penetration and consequently reducing the primary producer's path, and/or reducing shelters
31 and crypsis of detritivorous invertebrates fostering their consumption by fish and bullfrogs. Another possible mechanism
32 could be the transformation of detritus into an important biomass of bullfrog larvae, whose skin or secretions could be
33 consumed by fish. Future studies of stable isotopes with a greater number of evaluated communities, as well as lipid profile
34 studies (Whiles et al. 2010) of both species and mesocosm experiments (Dodd 2010) could shed light on these hypotheses.

35 Not all features of biodiversity organization are equally sensible to invasion effects. In this sense, having reported the
36 impact of invasions on different components of biodiversity (Lockwood et al. 2006), there is a need for the evaluation of
37 those attributes that remain invariant after invasions. Particularly, to those properties that if disrupted—e.g. decoupling of
38 energy channels—may determine an abrupt change in communities stability. The integration of energy pathways at higher
39 trophic positions was remarkably robust to *L. catesbeianus* invasion. Adult bullfrogs operate as top consumers in upper

1 trophic positions, coupling the energy channels. This functional role was performed by native predators such as fish, turtles,
2 and the aquatic frog *P. minuta* among uninvaded communities. The introduction of top predators has been associated here
3 and elsewhere with changes in the upper trophic level and in other components of the food web (Vander Zanden et al.
4 1999; Baxter et al. 2004). However, our results indicate that despite the impact on the invaded community with changes in
5 species composition, body size and biomass (Gobel et al. 2019a) this main feature of food web architecture is preserved.
6 The identification of structural aspects that are robust or vulnerable to invasion processes is key, both for understanding
7 the mechanisms behind the impact of invasions, and for understanding of trophic webs in general. In this sense, the present
8 study is supporting the coupling of energy channels by large predators as a backbone of food web architecture. Most of the
9 changes observed in the invaded trophic webs were dependent on body size. This is a key attribute in the food web structure
10 and function, and many traits scale with it (e.g. energetic demand, trophic interactions, movement capacity; see Brown et
11 al. 2004), therefore the understanding of the impact of invasions on food webs could also be improved by taking a size-
12 dependent perspective. Biodiversity architecture has shown some invariant organization in other features of community
13 organization (e.g. Marquet et al. 1995). Invariant attributes may be associated with tipping points in ecosystem
14 resistance/stability (Tylianakis et al. 2010; Rooney and McCann 2012). In this sense, it is an important aspect to understand
15 what happens if the impact of the invasions is strong enough to change these invariant characteristics. The bullfrog invasion
16 in Aceguá affects diversity and biomass patterns along certain trophic levels (Laufer and Gobel 2017; Gobel et al. 2019a),
17 but not the integration of energy channels. However, further habitat degradation and climate change may surpass
18 community capacity to preserve this feature of food webs, surpassing a tipping point after which the whole system is
19 strongly degraded (Jackson et al. 2017).

20

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1 **Figures**

2
 3 **Fig 1** Trophic position and energy sources in ponds invaded and not-invaded by bullfrog and with and without fishes. The
 4 $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ is presented as a function of the centered $\delta^{13}\text{C}$. The weight of the selected model was close to 1 ($w_i \sim 1$). In spite of
 5 turnover in the upper predator identity and community assembly among ponds, species at higher trophic positions are
 6 constrained to balance the use of alternative energy sources—the detritus (brown) and the producer (green) energy paths.

7
 8 **Fig 2** Proportion of biomass obtained from the detritus energy path for macroinvertebrates ($F_{1,50} = 20.0$, $p < 0.001$) and
 9 fishes ($F_{1,56} = 135.0$, $p < 0.001$) in communities invaded and uninvaded by bullfrogs. NI: Not-invaded; I: Invaded; NF: No
 10 fish; F: fishes.

1
 2 **Fig 3** Proportion of detritus energy sources in the biomass of each of the tropho-species along ponds. The results obtained
 3 from the Bayesian mixture models are shown using box plots for each pond. Invertebrates are detailed in yellow, fish in
 4 light blue, amphibians in green, turtles in purple, and the bullfrog in dark green. In amphibians, L indicates larval stage
 5 and P post-metamorphic.

7
 8 **Fig 4** Proportion of detritus supported biomass and trophic position in relation to body size for native assemblages:
 9 macroinvertebrates (Proportion of allochthonous supported biomass: $F_{2,49} = 16.3$; $P < 0.001$; $r\text{-sqrt} = 0.37$. Trophic
 10 position: $F_{3,46} = 6.8$, $P < 0.001$; $r\text{-sqrt} = 0.26$), native tadpoles (Proportion of allochthonous biomass: $F_{2,10} = 9.6$; $P =$
 11 0.004 ; $r\text{-sqrt} = 0.59$. Trophic position: $F_{3,9} = 13.2$, $P > 0.001$; $r\text{-sqrt} = 0.70$) and Characidae fishes (Proportion of
 12 allochthonous supported biomass: $F_{3,54} = 137$, $P < 0.001$; $r\text{-sqrt} = 0.88$. Trophic position: $F_{3,54} = 18.9$, $P < 0.001$; $r\text{-sqrt}$

1 = 0.48) in communities invaded (red) and uninvaded (blue) by bullfrogs. If there are no differences between invaded and
 2 uninvaded sites, it is shown as a black line. In the invertebrate figures, the point shapes indicate different taxonomic groups:
 3 *Belostoma* (filled square), Chironomidae (filled circle), Coenagrionidae (filled triangle), Corixidae (empty square),
 4 Curculionidae (empty circle), Ephemeroptera (empty triangle), Hyallela (asterisk), Notonectidae (cross)

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7 **Fig 5** Fraction of biomass supported by the detritus energy path and trophic position in relation to body size for post-
 8 metamorphs (Proportion of allochthonous biomass: $F_{1,18} = 7.7$, $P = 0.01$; $r\text{-sqr}t = 0.26$. Trophic position: $F_{1,18} = 0.5$; $P =$
 9 0.5 , $r\text{-sqr}t = -0.03$) and tadpoles (Proportion of allochthonous biomass: $F_{1,12} = 23.3$, $P < 0.001$; $r\text{-sqr}t = 0.63$. Trophic
 10 position: $F_{1,12} = 0.004$; $P = 0.9$; $r\text{-sqr}t = -0.08$) of the invasive bullfrog *Lithobates catesbeianus*